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IMPLEMENTING THE U.S. AGENCY FOR HEALTHCARE RESEARCH AND QUALITY'S
HOSPITAL 2.0 SURVEY ON PATIENT SAFETY CULTURE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

This project used the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture 2.0 to assess the current patient safety culture (PSC) and attitudes among Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs) and physician anesthesiologists at two acute care Southern California facilities. Additional aims included assessing demographic data, comparing responses by provider type across survey dimensions, and providing recommendations for improvement. 121 surveys were electronically distributed and yielded a sample of 43 anesthesia practitioners (36% response rate) for this cross-sectional study design. 49% of survey participants responded positively to the overall “patient safety rating” of the department, demonstrating room for improvement. The dimensions (composite measures) with the highest positive responses were "teamwork" (71%) and "communication about error" (65%). In contrast, the lowest positive responses were seen in the dimensions of "staffing and workplace" (21%) and "hospital management support for patient safety" (33%). The attitudes of CRNAs concerning the overall “patient safety rating” were lower than those of physician anesthesiologists. However, the absolute difference between these averages was not statistically significant ($p = .53$). There were no statistically significant differences in the dimensions of “teamwork,” “staffing and workplace,” and “hospital management support for patient safety” between CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists. A thematic analysis of free-text comments resulted in three main themes: staffing shortages, continuous organizational learning, and leaders' lack of support for patient safety and communication openness. Based on the study results, the authors recommend that improvement efforts focus on improving staffing and leadership support for patient safety to create meaningful positive changes in the facility’s PSC.

Keywords: Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, AHRQ, Survey on Patient Safety Culture, SOPS Hospital Survey 2.0, patient safety culture

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Background

Patient safety is a cornerstone of effective healthcare. However, lapses in patient safety do occur and contribute to significant morbidity and mortality (Azyabi et al., 2021). Lapses range from medication errors to the development of infections. Before implementing patient safety improvements at any level within a healthcare system, it is essential to assess the current culture of that organization. Healthcare workers are usually the first to identify patient safety issues, and their reporting on patient safety culture (PSC) has been linked to better patient outcomes (Lee et al., 2019). By identifying the strengths of PSC and targeting areas for improvement within an organization, hospitals can ultimately improve the delivery of quality patient care (Mrayyan, 2022). This doctoral project paper will discuss the background and significance of PSC, review current literature surrounding patient safety, discuss the methods of assessing the PSC within a healthcare microsystem, and provide recommendations for future patient safety implementation projects.

Patient Safety Culture

Patient safety culture is the composite of attitudes, practices, and beliefs of healthcare practitioners or a specific facility regarding patient safety (Mrayyan, 2022). Lee et al. (2019) stated that a PSC focuses on averting harm and adverse events (AE). Typically, the attitudes of one provider do not define PSC; rather, it is the sum and interactions of all providers' behaviors (Mrayyan, 2022). Before developing implementation strategies to generate change, a keen understanding of the current PSC is imperative.

The literature presents several predictors and factors contributing to a positive PSC. The Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture (SOPS) 2.0 also emphasizes these predictors (AHRQ, 2022a). Lee et al. (2019) indicate that

there is an inverse relationship between the total PSC and medication errors. When the PSC is reported as more positive, there is a decrease in medication errors (Lee et al., 2019). Other factors contributing to PSC include teamwork and communication, also assessed in the Hospital SOPS 2.0 (AHRQ, 2022a; Azyabi et al., 2021).

The challenges of an increasingly complex healthcare system have driven many organizations to invest in promoting an enhanced safety culture. Among those challenges are reported preventable AEs due to unsafe practices that threaten patient safety and the quality of care delivered (Azyabi et al., 2021). According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2019), one in ten inpatients in developed countries is estimated to experience harm, with 50% of those cases being preventable. Investigations of adverse healthcare events often implicate a suboptimal PSC as a significant causative factor (Danielsson et al., 2019). Several sequelae have been linked to reduced staff perception of safety culture, including increased clinical errors, AEs, readmission rates, healthcare expenditures, and patient morbidity and mortality (Danielsson et al., 2019; Pimentel et al., 2021). Conversely, more favorable patient outcomes are associated with a higher level of perceived PSC (Reis et al., 2018).

High-risk and high-stress operative settings are especially vulnerable to deficiencies in team dynamics that uphold patient safety. Anesthesia providers have long been at the center of quality improvement efforts to mitigate anesthesia-related AEs resulting in patient harm (Anesthesia Patient Safety Foundation [APSF], n.d.). For example, prefilled medication syringes to reduce perioperative medication errors and improved physiological monitoring capabilities have significantly reduced mortality linked to anesthesia (APSF, n.d.; Liu & Larson, 2022). While efforts have improved anesthetic safety, preventable errors and deaths continue to occur

(Liu & Larson, 2022). This fact demands continued progress in the field of anesthesia (Liu & Larson, 2022).

Validated surveys have been globally utilized to assess PSC in diverse hospital settings. As opposed to qualitative approaches, surveys provide the advantage of user anonymity, allowing for a more honest reflection of provider perceptions (Reis et al., 2018). Anesthesia providers can use the validated Hospital SOPS 2.0 to assess their perception of PSC (Reis et al., 2018).

Problem Statement

While many studies have explored PSC within hospitals or patient care units, there is limited research regarding PSC among anesthesia departments (Pimentel et al., 2021). Organizational improvements in anesthetic patient safety can only be enacted by establishing a supportive and dynamic safety culture. Therefore, fostering a safety climate in the operative setting is critical to preventing perioperative errors and will require an understanding of anesthesia providers' current behaviors, attitudes, and beliefs regarding PSC within their organization (Pimentel et al., 2021).

Vigilant assessment of staff perceptions of PSC has been suggested to improve patient safety outcomes within hospital organizations (Mrayyan, 2022). Despite this, the number of high-quality, evidence-based studies on healthcare PSC remains limited (Arzahan et al., 2022). Improving hospitals' overall performance and patient safety outcomes is vital to providing high-quality care. Therefore, it is essential to address this knowledge gap to assess staff perceptions of PSC and identify strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

A knowledge gap exists regarding the PSC within an acute care hospital system in Southern California. Identifying the PSC strengths and weaknesses specific to the perioperative

environment within the facility is imperative. The organization can tailor interventions to the environment and improve perioperative staff behaviors/attitudes and organizational safety culture. These interventions aim to improve patient safety outcomes and quality care delivery.

Like other healthcare professionals, anesthesia providers are not afforded immunity to the challenges associated with substandard system processes or human error. Several factors have challenged efforts to improve patient safety, such as the ever-increasing productivity demands of the operating room, more complex surgical techniques, and an influx of higher acuity surgical patients (Pimentel et al., 2021). However, safety initiatives have placed a renewed focus on changing systemic processes that predispose practitioners to error rather than viewing unsafe events as a result of individual provider lapses (Liu & Larson, 2022).

Significance

There is a lack of understanding of the PSC within an anesthesia department at two acute care facilities in Southern California. Recent literature suggests that PSC strengths include non-punitive responses to errors and teamwork within hospital units (Mrayyan, 2022). Non-punitive approaches to errors increase the likelihood of appropriate reporting, allowing root-cause analysis to identify solutions for problems (Mrayyan, 2022). Additionally, non-punitive processes ensure errors are reported earlier and create a blame-free environment, improving risk management (Mrayyan, 2022).

Other areas for improvement include open communication, teamwork among units, and the manager's expectations in promoting PSC (Mrayyan, 2022). Qualitative and quantitative measurement of perceived PSC aids in targeting areas for improvement. The validated Hospital SOPS 2.0 tool allows for identifying and synthesizing interventions to improve the safety culture.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to assess the current PSC and attitudes among anesthesia providers in an acute care Southern California facility to understand how the culture can contribute to future change.

Project Objectives

The objectives of this doctoral project were to:

- Evaluate areas of strengths and weaknesses in perceived PSC among anesthesia providers (defined as both certified registered nurse anesthetists and anesthesiologists) as outlined by the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 survey responses
- Assess demographic data and differences in responses for each composite score
- Provide evidence-based recommendations for future patient safety improvement projects.

Supporting Framework

Supporting frameworks guide quality improvement projects to allow for clear direction as a project advances. For this project on assessing PSC, the revised version of the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice was the chosen framework to support the project's goals. This section will discuss the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice, outline and discuss each step of the model, and review how each step was applied to this project.

Background of Iowa Model

Using a supporting framework allowed for structure in developing a project, and the Iowa model provided a systematic approach to project inception and execution. The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice was created in 1994 by Titler and her associates at the University of Iowa (Titler et al., 1994). The model has its basis in two other theories and models: The Quality

Assurance Model Using Research and Roger's Diffusion of Innovations theory (Titler et al., 1994). The Iowa Model focuses on translating research into practice using nurses and others at the unit level (Titler et al., 1994). Development of the model included using triggers—identified problems through patient outcome data, observation, or acquired knowledge via recent literature (Titler et al., 1994). These triggers spurred process improvement ideas intended to result in a practice change.

Revisions to the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice occurred in 2015 as a response to the transformations and advancements in healthcare and the development of implementation science as a discipline (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The revised model (Figure 1) used in this project focused on simplifying the initial model for easier usability. These simplifications include reducing the number of triggers listed, combining steps such as evidence acquisition and appraisal, and adding the step of stating the research problem (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The result was a more streamlined model that still provided a systematic approach to investigating a research problem and converting the results into a sustained change.

Identifying Trigger Issues

In the roadmap of the Iowa Model, the first step was to identify the trigger issue. According to the original Iowa Model by Titler et al. (1994), these trigger issues could be identified using knowledge-based or problem-based triggers. In the revised Iowa Model, triggers may come from sources such as new data; an initiative at the organizational, state, or national level; new regulations by an accrediting body; or issues identified within a clinical setting or patient care (Cullen et al., 2018). Identification of the trigger for this project stemmed from two areas. The first was the organizational commitment of the healthcare organization to foster a culture of safe patient care and continuously improve in this area (Kaiser Permanente, 2018). The

second was specific to the facility where the project was implemented. A needs assessment discussion between the project team lead and the Director of Anesthesia identified an opportunity to assess PSC in the anesthesia department to guide future patient safety improvements (M. Gabot, personal communication, October 15, 2022). Additionally, the National Committee for Quality Assurance health insurance plan ratings for the two acute care hospitals in Southern California from 2019 to 2020 revealed a performance score of 2.0 for “coordination of care” (National Committee for Quality Assurance, 2022). The lower performance score may have been attributed to a lower PSC and the dimension of teamwork.

Stating the Question or Purpose

The second step in the Iowa Model was to state the question or purpose. Cullen et al. (2018) wrote that forming a question or purpose for a project was critical to leading the project and providing a clear vision for goals. The Iowa Model included stating the project’s purpose in order to concentrate better efforts on finding evidence and assessing if the trigger was a priority for study (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). After identifying the PSC triggers, this project assessed the current PSC at two sister hospitals in Southern California by administering the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 amongst anesthesia providers and analyzing the results.

Priority of Topic

Assessing if a topic is a priority to an organization or research group was the first decision point in the revised Iowa Model. Answering this question determined if the project was worth pursuing or if another research question should be asked (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Determining if a research question is a priority can occur by considering the breadth of the issue and its effect on patient care, coupled with the values and goals of an organization (Cullen et al., 2018). In determining if the topic of PSC in anesthesia was a priority to the

healthcare organization, the group reviewed the organization's mission and goals regarding patient safety. It looked at the current understanding of the PSC of the hospital in Southern California. The team also made early attempts to identify the key stakeholder of the Director of Anesthesia at the specific facility for the project and appraised if the research project aligned with the department's needs. The project team determined that the PSC of the anesthesia department and the subsequent influence of the PSC on patient safety outcomes was unknown. The literature supports assessing a PSC to guide future quality improvement endeavors (Kakeman et al., 2021). By evaluating the PSC of the specific acute care sister hospitals, the team identified strengths and weaknesses in the PSC and identified where gaps in patient safety existed. This assessment helped guide future patient safety improvement measures and helped cultivate an interest in PSC.

Formation of a Team

After assessing the priority of a topic, the next step was to form a team. Forming an effective team hinges on several factors: composition and skill mix, group size, and team leadership (Cullen et al., 2018). Additionally, the Iowa Model advocated for the prompt identification and involvement of key stakeholders in the varying stages of the project to build a more efficacious team (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2018). The development of this project's team began with the team lead, Dr. Mark Gabot, DNP, CRNA, FAANA from the Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA), who helped to identify the trigger issue and scope of the problem. Dr. Rachel McClanahan, DNP, RN, NCSN, served as a team member and faculty advisor from California State University, Fullerton (CSUF). Other team members included: Sarah Evangelista, BSN, RN; Garrick Liang, BSN, RN; and Brandy Plascencia, BSN, RN. Chloe Gomez, MSN,

CRNA, was a KPSA clinical coordinator and a key stakeholder in the development of this project and, as such, was included as a team member.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize the Body of Evidence

The Iowa model emphasized the need to evaluate, appraise, and synthesize the body of evidence, including determining the quantity and scope of evidence (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). A search for relevant peer-reviewed publications was carried out using key pertinent terms and specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. The team methodically appraised and graded the available literature to determine the evidence's inherent strength, quality, limitations, and subsequent level of evidence. The evidence comprised mainly cross-sectional studies, randomized controlled trials, and systematic reviews. Thereafter, the publications were organized into a table of evidence, where several themes inherent to a culture of safety emerged. A synthesis of the evidence suggested that measuring PSC within healthcare organizations was critical to reducing AEs and improving the delivery of high-quality care (Aburumman et al., 2019; Arzahan et al., 2022; Azyabi et al., 2021). Additionally, PSC assessment helped determine the effectiveness of implementing various patient safety interventions (Azyabi et al., 2021).

Sufficient Evidence

After appraising and synthesizing the data, the Iowa Model required the team to determine if sufficient evidence existed to implement a proposed change (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). According to the model, a paucity of evidence supporting the recommended change required the team to conduct further research (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). However, the team's extensive literature review provided sufficient evidence to suggest that assessing PSC within various healthcare environments was paramount to mitigating the incidence of unfavorable outcomes and medical errors (Aburumman et al., 2019; Arzahan et al.,

2022; Azyabi et al., 2021). The assessment of PSC has been demonstrated to be a vital first step in quality improvement efforts aimed at enhancing care delivery systems and patient safety (Aburumman et al., 2019; Arzahan et al., 2022; Azyabi et al., 2021). In the operating room, surgeons and anesthesiologists' poor perception of PSC had detrimental effects on provider productivity and safe healthcare practices (Aouicha et al., 2022).

Evidence supporting the reliability and validity of the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 for PSC assessment was adequately established (Sorra & Dyer, 2010; Wagner et al., 2009; Waterson et al., 2019). Consequently, the team adopted the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 survey to explore anesthesia providers' perceptions of PSC within the project implementation site. The Iowa Model suggested that new knowledge and evidence could help propel a practice change forward (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

Design and Pilot the Practice Change

Once it had been established that sufficient evidence existed to support a change project, the revised Iowa Model suggested the next step be the creation of a pilot study that tested the practicability of the proposed change or facilitated answering the research question (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017; Titler et al., 1994). According to Titler et al. (1994), a small-scale pilot study helped researchers assess if intervention and adjustments needed to be made in the study without adversely affecting a larger population.

The project's design focused on collecting baseline data on PSC via implementing the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 to help with future quality improvement projects. The project team considered the resources needed to disperse and collect the surveys, the relevance of the research topic to the anesthesia department of the two acute care hospitals in Southern California, and the timeframe necessary for the completion of the study. Additionally, the project factored in

institutional review board (IRB) approval and approval by the organization before conducting the study, as well as ethical considerations (Cullen et al., 2018).

Appropriateness for Adoption in Practice

Once the design of a project has been established and a pilot has been conducted, the next step was a decision point in the Iowa Model: Is it appropriate to adopt a change in practice?

According to the revised Iowa Model, evaluating the appropriateness for adoption in practice should occur by assessing the results of the pilot coupled with evidence from the literature and the application to the studied population (Cullen et al., 2018).

Based on the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 results, the team's recommended changes were appropriate for adoption in clinical practice because it addressed a potential gap in knowledge regarding PSC at the facility where the project was implemented. As maintaining patient and anesthesia provider safety was a priority goal at the two sister hospitals in Southern California, the clinical change to improve PSC aligned with the overarching goals of the specific healthcare system (Schwartz et al., 2018). The delivery of safe patient care within the perioperative setting was essential to protect patients from undue harm and anesthesia providers from the risk of liability and malpractice claims (Haas et al., 2018). After the project, the team's findings may improve PSC at two acute care sister hospitals in Southern California by reducing medication errors, improving error reporting rates, or improving teamwork communication between interdisciplinary departments. These factors have been suggested to increase PSC, which would validate the appropriateness of adopting the research findings into clinical practice.

Integrate and Sustain the Practice Change

After determining the appropriateness of a practice change, the next step in the Iowa Model was to integrate and sustain the practice change (Cullen et al., 2018). Using the revised

Iowa Model, the project team's recommendations for improving PSC were presented to the anesthesia staff at Kaiser Permanente San Bernardino County (KP SBC) according to the design protocol. Integrating and sustaining practice changes to improve staffing and leadership support for PSC entails identifying, engaging, and gaining buy-in from key stakeholders, including anesthesia department leaders, providers, and support staff. Buy-in can be achieved through efforts to improve knowledge of the implications of improving staffing and PSC. Examples of knowledge campaigns include educational staff meetings, e-mails, and department champion efforts (Cullen et al., 2022). Ingraining the proposed recommendations into the culture at KP SBC requires a mutual commitment from leadership and frontline staff alike. Shared governance through regularly held staffing and retention committee meetings can facilitate brainstorming, monitoring of key staffing indicators, regular check-ins on measured progress, accountability on mutually set deadlines, and sustained recruitment and retention efforts. Efforts to improve staffing, such as strengthening partnerships with anesthesia schools and ramping recruitment efforts through these partnerships, must be hardwired to achieve long-standing results.

Leadership participation in shared governance allows leaders to impress upon staff the organization's commitment to safety. Additionally, regularly scheduled meetings give providers a continued avenue to impart suggestions regarding their practice environment, while leaders are also allowed to provide closed-loop communication regarding staff concerns (Tang & Hudson, 2019). Enacting departmental policies that improve work-life balance, such as allowing part-time status or provider-driven schedule flexibility, can lead to sustained organizational change (Cullen et al., 2022). Additionally, integrating wellness-based interventions during new hire orientation can set a precedent for these interventions' value in building resilience and avoiding burnout within the workplace (Cullen et al., 2022).

Sustaining the proposed practice change involves monitoring key indicators of the quality improvement change by evaluating staff perceptions of PSC at regularly scheduled intervals. This may be achieved through the monthly assessment of turnover and retention trends, staff interviews, or additional PSC surveys. Monthly progress of the practice change would be evaluated using surveys disseminated to anesthesia providers using a 5-point Likert scale or repeat AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 to rate staff perceptions of PSC. These results would be compared to pre- and post-implementation data to determine whether a significant change in PSC has occurred within the organization. If significant progress has yet to occur, monthly evaluation of PSC allows the team to re-direct their focus toward interventions that may improve PSC more effectively.

The literature suggests that practice changes are sustained when the practice is ingrained into organizational culture (Colquhoun et al., 2017). The proposed practice change must be adopted into the culture at KP SBC through the continual promotion of PSC by clinical leaders and anesthesia department staff to ensure that the change is lasting and permanent (Colquhoun et al., 2017).

Dissemination of Findings

The dissemination of research findings is an integral part of the research process and the final step of the Iowa model (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). Sharing the results with the public allowed other researchers to appraise the findings, test new hypotheses, and expand upon existing knowledge (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The project team disseminated their findings at the CSUF School of Nursing DNP CRNA dissemination day and to the anesthesia department at the sister facilities in San Bernardino County, California. In addition, the project team plans to submit a manuscript for publication in the International Student Journal of Nurse

Anesthesia and present a poster for display at the Azusa Pacific University (APU) Nursing Research Symposium.

Adoption of The Iowa Model in Research

The Iowa Model has been widely adopted to guide and effectuate practice changes in various healthcare settings (Lemus et al., 2018). The use of the model has garnered positive recognition in quality improvement efforts due to its streamlined and stepwise approach to implementing evidence-based practice changes and its adaptability (Servas et al., 2022). In particular, the Iowa Model has been instrumental in targeting high-yield nursing interventions to improve patient safety and outcomes (Lemus et al., 2018; Saqe-Rockoff et al., 2018; Servas et al., 2022).

Lemus et al. (2018) applied the Iowa Model in their design and implementation of a nursing practice guideline to improve the safety index of nursing care provided to patients with a high risk of obstructive sleep apnea (OSA). Chart audits over six months revealed a 27% incidence of postoperative cardiopulmonary complications among patients deemed high-risk for OSA, making the topic a triggering issue and safety priority for the organization (Lemus et al., 2018). The authors formulated a nursing guideline consisting of evidence-based recommendations in screening, handoff, education, and postoperative care (Lemus et al., 2018). The results demonstrated a reduction in postoperative complications after guideline implementation from 27% to 14.6% (Lemus et al., 2018). These significant practice changes, mediated by the Iowa model, improved nurses' knowledge and awareness of the risks posed by OSA in the perioperative period (Lemus et al., 2018).

Saqe-Rockoff et al. (2018) utilized the Iowa model to implement a thermoregulation checklist after identifying a problem in timely temperature assessment and initiating rewarming

interventions among vulnerable trauma patients. Implementing the evidence-based practice checklist consisted of appropriate guidance regarding rewarming measures, temperature monitoring, and documentation intervals (Saqe-Rockoff et al., 2018). Following the implementation of the thermoregulatory checklist and education of nursing staff, there was a 19% increase in core temperature assessment ($p < 0.001$) and increased use of warming blankets ($p = 0.002$) within a year (Saqe-Rockoff et al., 2018). Using the model was instrumental in improving the nursing management of hypothermic trauma patients at minimal cost to the organization (Saqe-Rockoff et al., 2018).

Lastly, Servas et al. (2022) employed the Iowa Model to devise and introduce an evidence-based handoff pause and standardized handoff procedure in the post-anesthesia care unit (PACU). The authors identified lapses in handoff communication among PACU nurses and operating room staff, namely PACU nurses connecting patients to monitoring devices and receiving handoff reports simultaneously (Servas et al., 2022). Servas et al. (2022) noted that a pause allowed PACU nurses to dedicate time to settling and connecting patients to various monitoring equipment and increased concentration during the handoff report. Further, a standardized perioperative handoff report can mitigate the incidence of postoperative AEs due to communication lapses. These changes, mediated through the Iowa model framework, improved PACU nurses, operating room nurses, and anesthesia provider satisfaction with handoff procedures (Servas et al., 2022).

Review of Literature

A literature review was conducted for this project to search for relevant, current publications related to PSC in the hospital setting. The following databases were used: PubMed and CINAHL. Search terms and combinations of terms included “leadership AND patient safety culture,” “patient safety,” “patient safety culture,” “patient safety culture anesthesia,” “safety culture,” “safety climate,” and “Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture.” The inclusion criteria for PubMed and CINAHL searches included peer-reviewed clinical trials, randomized control trials, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and mixed-method studies published in English from 2017 to the present. Exclusion criteria included articles not published in English and articles published before 2017. Opinion articles, commentary, and editorials were likewise excluded from the search.

A PubMed search using the inclusion and exclusion criteria yielded 336 results for “patient safety culture” and 37 results for “Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture.” A CINAHL search with the specified criteria yielded 2,883 results for “patient safety culture” and “safety climate.” Common themes that emerged included the non-punitive response to errors, teamwork dynamics and provider engagement, organizational learning, communication, leadership commitment to PSC, and the validity of the Hospital SOPS 2.0 tool in evaluating PSC. A total of 18 studies were included in this review of the literature. Four systematic reviews, one randomized control trial, seven cross-sectional surveys, two mixed-method studies with cross-sectional surveys, one retrospective analysis, one longitudinal study, one descriptive correlational study, and one qualitative study on leadership were used.

Nonpunitive Response to Errors/Error Reporting

Current literature suggests that a non-punitive approach to errors increases the likelihood of near-miss and error reporting among healthcare providers (Kwan et al., 2021; Sanchis et al., 2020; Tlili et al., 2022; Zabin et al., 2022). Tlili et al. (2022) conducted a cross-sectional, mixed methods study and concluded that the issue of error under-reporting often stems from a culture of blame and fear. Additionally, the lack of feedback and learning culture may promote the under-reporting of errors, as providers may no longer see the importance of reporting errors (Tlili et al., 2022). Similarly, Zabin et al. (2022) found a statistically significant relationship between staff feedback and communication about errors and PSC. Management should have a non-punitive response approach to remediation when errors occur, ultimately improving PSC (Zabin et al., 2022).

The organizational culture of a hospital must also be considered (Kwan et al., 2021; Sanchis et al., 2020). Kwan et al. (2021) concluded that organizational cultures must promote tolerance for mistakes while holding individuals accountable for medical errors. Organizational culture may significantly impact the incidence of error reporting (Sanchis et al., 2020). Current research recommends promoting a non-punitive environment that minimizes individuals at fault and examines the system as a whole for areas of improvement (Sanchis et al., 2020). When organizations establish a blame-free culture, there is an increased probability that safety events are reported, suggesting an overall increase in PSC within the hospital (Kwan et al., 2021).

Teamwork Dynamics and Provider Engagement

Numerous studies also suggest that teamwork dynamics play an integral role in promoting PSC (Kwan et al., 2021; Weng et al., 2022; Wong et al., 2021). Kwan et al. (2021) concluded that cooperation between various hospital departments is essential to achieve PSC.

The researchers concluded that a multidisciplinary team with good communication can promote the continuous implementation of quality care improvement (Kwan et al., 2021). Similarly, Weng et al. (2022) conducted a retrospective analysis of multidisciplinary teams working in general wards and found a positive correlation between higher team performance and increased perception of PSC. The researchers found that interventions to improve PSC should primarily focus on improving collaboration and communication between team dynamics (Weng et al., 2022). Additionally, Wong et al. (2021) conducted a longitudinal study to assess the perceptions of PSC among hospital staff and found a theme of teamwork and communication throughout disciplines and units, with allied staff holding the highest positive attitudes towards management and teamwork.

Increased provider engagement levels have also been suggested to improve PSC within hospitals. Boussat et al. (2021) conducted a cross-sectional study to assess the effect of provider involvement in feedback committee activities and PSC scores. Boussat et al. (2021) found that providers who participated in root cause analysis activities showed higher perceptions of PSC, suggesting that staff who are more involved within the hospital may increase overall PSC within organizations.

Organizational Learning

Numerous studies have demonstrated a connection between active continuous improvement processes in an organization and a positive perception of increased patient safety (Amiri et al., 2018; Aouicha et al., 2022; Ayzabi et al., 2021; Kakeman et al., 2021; Zabin et al., 2022). As an organization intentionally commits to increasing patient safety, the perception by staff becomes more positive (Amiri et al., 2018; Kakeman et al., 2021; Zabin et al., 2022). The subsequent increase in positive perception of PSC leads to a decrease in AEs (Kakeman et al.,

2021; Lee et al., 2019). Leadership can help improve organizational learning and continuous improvement by using validated quality improvement tools in process improvement measures and creating systems to prevent errors (Sanchis et al., 2020). Buy-in by leadership to improve organizational learning and patient safety can set the tone for organizational learning and provide a positive perception to healthcare staff about the PSC of the organization (Sanchis et al., 2020).

Part of organizational learning comes from learning from theory and translating it into practice or reducing the theory-practice gap (Aouicha et al., 2022). Concerns in the literature about translating theory into practice regarding patient safety abound (Aouicha et al., 2022; Kwan et al., 2021). One example of improving organizational learning is educational programs that empower healthcare staff. Programs such as Team Strategies and Tools to Enhance Performance and Patient Safety (TeamSTEPPS) can facilitate the growth of hospital staff to voice concerns about patient safety and awareness of each staff member's role in preventing safety errors (Amiri et al., 2018). Wong et al. (2021) discuss the impact of encouraging staff to attend workshops on Lean and Six Sigma quality improvement methodologies to help transition the theory of these programs into practice. Further research should study the effects of implementing programs that promote the growth of organizational learning on PSC.

Communication

In conjunction with organizational learning and continuous improvement, enhancement of communication can lead to an increased perception of PSC. Current literature demonstrates a low perception among studies of communication openness in an organization (Aouicha et al., 2022; Kakeman et al., 2021; Tili et al., 2022). Hospital staff are afraid to speak up, often because of a lack of training or fear of repercussions (Amiri et al., 2018). Fragmentation of care via

inadequate communication can lead to many AEs and patient safety issues (Kakeman et al., 2021).

Suggestions in the literature for how to improve communication include the use of handoff tools. The Surgical Safety Checklist (SSC) has been suggested to standardize communication and decrease breakdowns among different disciplines in the operating room (Aouicha et al., 2022). The SSC used in conjunction with periodic briefings in the operating room can facilitate communication between staff and better patient outcomes (Aouicha et al., 2022). Another tool is the Situation, Background, Assessment, and Recommendation (SBAR) tool, which can facilitate handoff and diminish communication gaps (Amiri et al., 2018).

Educational programs can incorporate staff empowerment to voice concerns regarding patient safety issues (Amiri et al., 2018). Communication between management and staff should include quality improvement measures to enable mutual respect and openness between the two parties (Tili et al., 2022). Ensuring consistent and effective communication between all parties in a healthcare system will allow for more gaps to be filled and decrease AEs.

Leadership Commitment to Patient Safety Culture

Supportive leadership and an organization's commitment to safety are central to developing a positive PSC (Lotfi et al., 2018; Montminy, 2022; Ree & Wiig, 2019). A systematic review by Aburumman et al. (2019) explored various workplace interventions and their effects on safety culture. Interventions aimed at improving management commitment to and emphasis on safety were most effective, further outlining the critical role of healthcare leadership in improving safety culture (Aburumman et al., 2019). Influential leaders prioritize patient safety within their organization, allocate resources to monitor safety performance and implement system process improvements (Lotfi et al., 2018; Montminy, 2022).

Montminy (2022) asserts that leaders must be well-informed on policies and procedures about patient safety as doing so can improve uniformity in leadership guidance of practice expectations. Managers create policies and system processes that promote a safe practicing environment (Montminy, 2022; Ree & Wiig, 2019). Lotfi et al. (2018) found that management commitment to patient safety improved employee engagement, provider safety behaviors, and safety culture. Similarly, Ree and Wiig (2019) found that transformational leadership was the strongest positive predictor for PSC over job resources, work engagement, and job demands. Fostering a non-judgmental and trusting rapport between staff and leadership is essential to enhancing team cooperation, learning, and error-reporting by staff (Montminy, 2022). While adopting a non-punitive approach to medical errors is paramount, a delicate balance is merited to objectively distinguish blatant disregard for safety policies and procedures (Kwan et al., 2021; Montminy, 2022). Additionally, Ree and Wiig (2019) state that leader initiatives should balance staffing and job demands with providing job resources to positively impact PSC. This evidence suggests that healthcare leaders significantly influence organizational safety dynamics and, thus, may benefit from further training and education on how best to promote and develop a positive PSC (Montminy, 2022; Ree & Wiig, 2019).

Leaders can effectively demonstrate support for patient safety by providing adequate resources for delivering high-quality care, promoting staff engagement in safety initiatives, and allotting time with staff to communicate safety concerns (Lotfi et al., 2018; Ree & Wiig, 2019). More importantly, managers should creatively engage and communicate with frontline staff to model appropriate behaviors and impress upon them the organization's continued commitment to safety (Montminy, 2022). Although not all-inclusive, providing high-quality staff training, furnishing psychological safety through a blame-free environment, and creating error

management systems are examples of leadership support for a positive PSC (Lotfi et al., 2018; Ree & Wiig, 2019). One cross-sectional survey study found that implementing leadership safety rounds with closed-loop feedback communication resulted in a higher safety culture and provider engagement (Sexton et al., 2018). Managers are in an optimal position to listen to and understand their organization's safety challenges and aid in realizing change processes (Lotfi et al., 2018).

Validity of the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 Tool

The assessment of hospital safety culture has become increasingly important as healthcare organizations seek to enhance the quality of their healthcare services and minimize threats to patient safety (Waterson et al., 2019). As a result, PSC assessment has garnered increased momentum internationally (Reis et al., 2018). Various measurement tools have assisted in evaluating and monitoring the strengths, weaknesses, and trends in PSC among multiple hospital departments and across different healthcare organizations (Reis et al., 2018). However, the validity and reliability of tools designed to measure PSC have been highly criticized partly due to a disagreement among various healthcare disciplines on what components comprise a positive PSC (Waterson et al., 2019).

The AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 tool, a survey whose development was funded by the AHRQ, has been validated for use in PSC assessment in United States (U.S.) healthcare settings (Waterson et al., 2019; Reis et al., 2018). The Hospital SOPS 2.0 survey encompasses 40 survey items, with 32 being divided into ten composite measures (dimensions) of safety culture, including teamwork dynamics, error reporting communications, staffing, handoff, and leadership support concerning patient safety factors (AHRQ, 2022a). Respondent's characteristics are also assessed with six items, including but not limited to staff position, unit of work, and years of experience (AHRQ, 2022a). Since its creation in the U.S. in 2004, the Hospital SOPS 2.0 has

been translated into various languages and widely utilized in study publications spanning 60 countries (Reis et al., 2018).

In a systematic review analyzing the psychometric properties of the Hospital SOPS 2.0, Waterson et al. (2019) suggest exercising caution when utilizing the Hospital SOPS 2.0 and carefully considering the national healthcare context and differences incurred by translation. Nevertheless, several studies within the U.S. demonstrated high reliability and validity of the Hospital SOPS 2.0 (Sorra & Dyer, 2010; Wagner et al., 2009; Waterson et al., 2019). Sorra and Dyer (2010) found that Cronbach alpha values were greater than 0.70 across all survey dimensions, except for staffing (0.63). Similarly, Wagner et al. (2009) found Cronbach alpha values to be greater than or equal to 0.70 in all survey dimensions apart from organizational learning (0.69), suggesting high internal validity for the SOPS 2.0 tool and applicability for studies on assessing PSC (Waterson et al., 2019). Given the suggested reliability, validity, and limitations of the Hospital SOPS 2.0 within U.S. healthcare settings, it will be imperative and most effective to utilize a mixed methods approach to PSC assessment (Waterson et al., 2019).

Appraisal of Evidence

Most of the studies used in the review of literature were of level I or level II evidence, suggesting a high quality of evidence in the studies (Amiri et al., 2018; Aouicha et al., 2022; Kakeman et al., 2021; Reis et al., 2018; Tili et al., 2022; Waterson et al., 2019; Wong et al., 2021; Zabin et al., 2022). However, limitations among the studies did exist. One of the recurring limitations was the generalizability of results to other institutions because of the small sample size or the single study setting. A few studies were carried out within a single organization or had a smaller sample size, which reduced the overall external validity of the results as they cannot be generalized to other populations within the healthcare field (Amiri et al., 2018; Aouicha et al.,

2022; Boussat et al., 2021; Kakeman et al., 2021; Lotfi et al., 2018; Montminy, 2022; Ree & Wiig, 2019; Sanchis et al., 2020; Zabin et al., 2022).

Another area for improvement was the cross-sectional survey approach taken by many of the studies, which did not establish a cause-and-effect relationship between variables (Burlison et al., 2020; Kwan et al., 2021, Zabin et al., 2022). Cross-sectional surveys provide a snapshot of an organization's PSC but may not represent any organization's growth (Aouicha et al., 2022; Kakeman et al., 2021; Zabin et al., 2022). A longitudinal design was lacking in several studies, limiting the long-term assessment of a given intervention's effect on safety culture (Aburumman et al., 2019; Lotfi et al., 2018; Ree & Wiig, 2019). A longitudinal study design may allow for assessing PSC trends over time and after an intervention has been implemented within an organization. Moreover, several studies also demonstrated respondent bias in the results due to the Hawthorne effect (Aouicha et al., 2022; Ayzabi et al., 2021; Wong et al., 2021). The Hawthorne effect alters the participants' behavior in a study due to their awareness of being observed, which undermines the integrity of the results (Goodwin et al., 2017).

Despite the limitations noted in the studies, the studies add to the body of evidence supporting the assessment of PSC within an organization and reinforce the need for PSC. Likewise, the evidence underscored leadership's critical role in establishing a safety culture, namely listening to and understanding their organization's safety challenges and aiding in realizing change processes (Lotfi et al., 2018; Montminy, 2022).

Methods and Evaluation

The methods used to conduct a project are influenced by the design and tools used to collect data. When designing a project, the team must consider the benefits and limitations of the study design and identify the ethical considerations related to the topic and participants (Ross & Zaidi, 2019). The project aimed to a) evaluate anesthesia providers' attitudes toward PSC, b) assess demographic data and differences in responses for each composite score, and c) identify strengths and opportunities for improvement. This section will outline the study design, setting, sample and participants, ethical considerations, procedure, data collection, interventions, timeline, and data analysis and evaluation tools.

Design

This project was a cross-sectional survey study using the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0. A cross-sectional study is an observational research method that analyzes data across a sample population at one given time, providing a "snapshot" of the population of interest (Spector, 2019). A questionnaire survey design allowed the collection of data from a population of interest according to a predefined set of questions (Nardi, 2018). The benefits of using a cross-sectional survey study design include low cost, convenient data collection, minimal observer bias, and the ability to analyze multiple variables during data collection (Spector, 2019). However, limitations to this study design include sampling and non-response bias in which the sample does not represent the overall population. Thus, the results may not be generalizable (Nardi, 2018). Moreover, the cross-sectional method cannot determine causality nor analyze behavior over time (Spector, 2019).

Setting

The project was implemented in one anesthesiology department that provided anesthesia services at two sister hospitals within Southern California. The larger of the two facilities is a 314-bed acute care hospital that houses an adult, neonatal, and pediatric intensive care unit with a total of approximately 13 care units (Kaiser Permanente, 2013). The smaller facility, a 224-bed acute care hospital, provides medical specialties such as head and neck surgery, cardiology, and orthopedics (Kaiser Permanente, 2012). Both facilities in this project serve the San Bernardino County region and some areas of northern Riverside County in Southern California (Kaiser Permanente, 2019). The combined service area of both hospitals resulted in over two million patients served between 2012 to 2016, including some of the most under-resourced regions of California (Kaiser Permanente, 2019).

The specific project focused on the anesthesia department of the operating room. Both facilities provide routine and complex surgical services, with specialty surgeries including cardiothoracic surgery, joint replacements, and spinal neurosurgery (U.S. News and World Report, n.d.).

Sample and Participants

The target population for this project was anesthesia providers employed at two sister hospitals in Southern California from May to July 2023. The inclusion criteria for this project were Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs) and physician anesthesiologists within the anesthesiology department at the sister facilities. The inclusion criterion was a logical extension of the project's aim: assess the PSC within the anesthesia department and recommend improvements. Exclusion criteria for the project were staff within the anesthesiology department who do not provide direct anesthetic services to patients; for example, circulating operating room

nurses, scrub techs, surgeons, nurse practitioners, physician assistants, and anesthesia techs. At the time of survey design, 131 anesthesia providers on staff comprised the target population (M. Gabot, personal communication, November 30, 2022). Of the 131 anesthesia providers, 76 are CRNAs, and 55 are physician anesthesiologists (M. Gabot, personal communication, November 30, 2022). At the end of the survey collection, 121 providers met the inclusion criteria because of staff attrition.

Ethical Considerations

The Kaiser Permanente Southern California IRB and the CSUF IRB exemption was obtained. The IRB ensured that the project adhered to each institution's policies regarding project ethics (Bonnell & Smith, 2022). Exemption (approval of non-human subjects research) from the Kaiser Permanente Southern California and CSUF IRBs occurred before the implementation of the project.

The team obtained informed consent in the form of a disclaimer at the beginning of the survey indicating the risks and benefits, and that participation in the survey denoted consent by the individual. Participation was voluntary, and consent could be withdrawn at any time without consequence. The measures of informed consent and voluntary withdrawal respected the autonomy of the individual (Bonnell & Smith, 2022). All participants' data was de-identified and remained confidential. Data was stored on a secure server that required password-protected access. Data de-identification ensured that personal identification elements were removed from each survey (Chevier et al., 2019). Participants accessed the survey using their hospital email addresses. When used with the Qualtrics authenticator, the hospital email addresses tracked participation and prevented duplicate survey entries. However, the hospital email addresses were not linked to survey responses. The team members conducted data extraction and remained blind

to participant identifiers. Confidentiality was ensured by storing survey results in a password-protected computer. Surveys and all documentation were kept as records for a minimum of three years after completion (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2018).

Measures

The team adopted the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 to measure baseline data on PSC by qualified participants. The survey has been widely employed in publications worldwide, including in the U.S., the United Kingdom (U.K.), and Germany (Reis et al., 2018; Waterson et al., 2019). The SOPS 2.0 Hospital survey consisted of 40 items, with 32 items sorted into ten composite measures inherent to safety culture (AHRQ, 2022a). The ten measures included teamwork, staffing and work pace, organizational learning, response to error, leader support for patient safety, communication about errors, communication openness, reporting patient safety events, hospital management support for patient safety, and handoffs and information exchange (AHRQ, 2022a). The remaining eight items included identifying the number of events the respondent has reported over the last 12 months, the respondent's overall patient safety rating for their department, and six items outlining the respondent's background characteristics (AHRQ, 2022a). A 5-point Likert scale was utilized for both positively and negatively worded survey items depending on the measures of agreement (strongly disagree to strongly agree), frequency (never to always), or rating of patient safety grade (poor to excellent) (AHRQ, 2022a). A lower or higher percent positive response score indicated a lower or higher perception of PSC, respectively (AHRQ, 2022a).

The reliability and internal consistency of the SOPS 2.0 Hospital survey measures were indicated by Cronbach's alpha (α) coefficient values ranging from .70 to .84, except for the measure of staffing (Cronbach's $\alpha = .63$) (Sorra & Dyer, 2010; Waterson et al., 2019). However,

three of the eight U.S. studies included in the systematic review by Waterson et al. (2019) assessing the psychometric properties of the HSPSC reported a Cronbach α value between .71 and .81 for the measure of staffing. Cronbach α values demonstrating acceptable internal consistency and reliability ranged from .70 to .90 (Waterson et al., 2019). Therefore, no modifications were required due to the tool's established reliability in the English language (Reis et al., 2018; Waterson et al., 2019). According to the AHRQ (2022), the survey took 10 to 15 minutes to complete.

Procedure and Data Collection

After obtaining IRB approval, the project team electronically contacted and personally invited key stakeholders from the anesthesia departments of two sister hospitals in Southern California to partake in the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 survey. The team obtained permission letters for survey dissemination from each hospital's administrative leadership by holding a 15 to 30-minute PowerPoint presentation in the Spring of 2023 outlining the project's aims, relevancy, potential benefits, and recruitment and data collection process. After receiving approval for survey implementation from key stakeholders, the team moved forward with participant recruitment and data collection.

To promote survey participation, the team held an information session with the sister facilities' anesthesia providers, created recruitment flyers, ensured the survey could be completed within 10 to 15 minutes, and appointed local department champions to bolster interest. Department champions included two staff CRNAs, who, as clinical stakeholders, assisted in survey promotion efforts, survey distribution, and compiling a provider email contact list. The information session occurred during a combined CRNA and Anesthesiologist staff meeting. At the end of the meeting, 10 to 15 minutes were allotted to allow providers an

opportunity to complete the survey and provide feedback. The team also tracked survey response rates throughout the two-month data collection period to assess the need for heightened promotion efforts or an extension of the survey's open period. Flyers containing the information provided within the survey invitation email were posted in areas most visible to anesthesia providers, such as the anesthesia workrooms, break rooms, and designated bulletin boards. Staff incentives have effectively improved response rates (Smith et al., 2019). Thus, the team provided an incentive for participation in the survey with the approval of the IRB, such as an opportunity drawing for prizes of nominal value to increase response rates.

Data collection occurred during May 1st, 2023, and July 10th, 2023. The AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 surveys were initially electronically dispersed via an online Qualtrics survey sent to the email address on file for a convenience sample of CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists. Coordination between the project team and key stakeholders within the anesthesia departments assisted in the successful electronic dissemination of the survey. The electronic email comprised a detailed description of the aims of the project, inclusion and exclusion criteria, disclosure of participant risks and benefits, and informed consent indicating that participation was entirely voluntary and confidential. The team also included any incentives approved by the IRB, a disclosure indicating that results would be reported collectively and confidentially, and a link to the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 questionnaire via the survey platform Qualtrics (Qualtrics, Provo, Utah). Subsequent weekly email reminders for voluntary survey completion were implemented starting the week following initial survey dissemination.

This project focused on collecting baseline data regarding PSC in the anesthesia department and evaluating the data. After the survey period ended, the surveys were reviewed for completeness. After receiving all completed surveys, the team excluded surveys determined to be

invalid, namely surveys that were not entirely completed. The final response rate was determined as a percentage of the CRNAs and anesthesiologists within the anesthesia department.

The team analyzed the included surveys for demographic data, average scores for each dimension of the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0, and coding of any comments for thematic analysis. After analysis of the baseline data, recommendations for strengths and weaknesses were compiled and shared with the anesthesia department.

Timeline

The project began with a proposal defense in December 2022, as shown in Figure 2. The team presented the proposal defense to CSUF, and Kaiser School of Anesthesia (KPSA) faculty. After proposal approval, the team applied for approval from the Kaiser Permanente IRB in January 2023. Subsequent applications to the CSUF IRB occurred in February 2023. In March 2023, the team inputted the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 unchanged onto Qualtrics and began formatting the survey for distribution to the provider's email address. Once IRB approval was received, the team discussed the survey implementation with anesthesia providers at the two hospitals in Southern California in April of 2023 during a staff meeting and then began distributing the survey. The survey included an open period from May 2023 to July 2023. In July of 2023, the final collection of the surveys and data analysis began. The data analysis continued through the Fall of 2023. Based on its findings, the team created a final written paper and conducted a project defense in December 2023 for CSUF and KPSA faculty. Dissemination of the findings occurred after the completion of the project and the final project defense. Dissemination of findings will occur in the Spring of 2024. During this time, plans for further evolution of the project with future cohorts will occur.

Data Analysis and Evaluation

Data analysis for the project included two parts: demographic data from participants and scores for each composite measure of the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 (Figure 3). The demographic data from participants included the categorization of staff position, the unit, the number of years worked at the hospital, the number of years worked in the unit, and the number of hours worked per week at the hospital (AHRQ, 2022b). The team used descriptive statistics to analyze the demographic data included in the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0. Aggregate data as percentages for demographic data using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Statistics software for Windows version 29 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY) were compiled. Using the 5-point Likert scale, the average score of each composite measure of the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 was calculated and reported. The assessment of average scores helped assess the organization's PSC by providing measurable scores on areas of PSC. The evaluation included: a) reviewing the highest and lowest composite measures, b) comparing composite measures between demographic subgroups, and c) exploring correlations between demographics and composite measure scores. Gabot (2023), in a similar study of the 2021 AHRQ SOPS Hospital 2.0 results, compared differences in perception of safety culture between types of anesthesia providers via secondary analysis. This project also benefited from using the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U tests to compare the results of an ordinal or continuous dependent variable (e.g., 5-point Likert scale composite measures) (University of Utah, 2022). For example, differences in reporting between CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists on PSC which achieved the aim of assessing differences in demographic subtypes. The non-parametric Kruskal Wallis test was also used to compare composite measures between varying levels within demographic subgroups, specifically differences between tenure level and perceptions of PSC. Spearman rank

correlation was used to explore relationships between composite measures. The organization of the results for demographic data and mean composite scores of each dimension was presented in tables for easier readability. Lastly, a thematic analysis was performed to explore participant comments on their perception of hospital patient safety.

To complete the aim of providing recommendations on gaps in PSC and areas of improvement, the team evaluated the data for dimensions that scored the highest and lowest based on mean scores. These dimensions provided insight into areas of strength or weakness for the department and allowed the team to provide recommendations on improving PSC.

A thematic analysis was also conducted on the free-text survey comments to identify themes related to respondents' perceptions of PSC. Thematic analyses aim to interpret and explain data to identify codes, themes, and patterns within data sets (Braun et al., 2023). All respondents signed an informed consent document linked to their hospital email addresses. Free-text survey comments at the end of each survey were obtained after data de-identification and personal identification elements were removed. As the data set included only five free-text comments, the team conducted the initial open coding of the comments. Open coding is used when researchers do not have pre-set codes, but rather, codes are developed and modified as they work through the coding process (Braun et al., 2023). Analysis of the free-text survey comments revealed the following emerging themes, including staffing shortages, supervisor and manager support for clinical safety concerns, and organizational learning and continuous improvement. Each member of the project team reviewed assigned themes to preclude the introduction of bias and ensure validity of the results.

Results

Demographic Characteristics

Of the respondents, 37 (86%) were Advanced Practice Registered Nurses (ARNPs) and six (14%) were physician anesthesiologists. All respondents reported working in an anesthesiology department and having direct contact with patients. The majority of respondents ($n = 18$, 42%) had worked in their current hospital for six to 10 years. Likewise, the majority of respondents ($n = 17$, 40%) had worked in their current department for six to 10 years. Over half (53%) of the survey respondents reported working more than 40 hours per week. Regarding safety event reporting, at least half of respondents ($n = 22$, 51%) had reported one to two safety events in the last 12 months. Table 1 provides a complete overview of the background and demographic characteristics of the survey respondents.

Composite Measures and Averages

The AHRQ SOPS 2.0 categorizes the areas of patient safety into ten composite measures. One of the aims of the project was to evaluate areas of strengths and weaknesses in perceived PSC among anesthesia providers (defined as both CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists) as outlined by the AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 survey responses.

After survey results were collected and results were averaged, Teamwork had the highest composite average, with 71% of individuals responding positively. Of the Teamwork composite, the average score (4.11) for the item “during busy times, staff in this unit help each other” was relatively high compared to other items within the composite. Based on the five-point Likert scale, this indicates that respondents generally agree with the item. Another high-scoring question from the composite “in this unit, we work together as an effective team” with an aggregate score of 3.86, reflecting again respondents’ positive belief in the teamwork aspect of

the facility's patient safety rating (Table H1). The second highest scoring composite measure was that of Communication About Error, with 65% of individuals responding positively.

Conversely, the lowest composite measures were Staffing and Workplace (20% of participants responded positively). In Staffing and Workplace, the average score (1.86) for the item "in this unit, we have enough staff to handle the workload" was relatively low compared to other items in the composite. Based on the five-point Likert scale, this indicates that participants generally disagree with the item. All other questions within the composite measure had below-average aggregate scores, demonstrating a negative association between the composite measure and the PSC of the facility (Table H2). The second lowest-scoring composite measure was Hospital Management Support for Patient Safety, with 33% of participants responding positively. All other composite measure scores can be found in Appendix H.

Patient Safety Rating

Within the AHRQ SOPS 2.0, participants were asked, "How would you rate your unit/work area on patient safety?" using a one to five Likert scale. Of the participants, 49% responded positively ("excellent" or "very good"). All respondents' average patient safety rating for the department (or unit) was 3.30.

Normality of Patient Safety Rating Data

Tests for normality were performed prior to comparative and correlation analyses. A graphical assessment of normality using a histogram of patient safety ratings from all participants indicated that the composite data was not normally distributed, as shown in Figure 4. The Shapiro-Wilk test rejected the null hypothesis that the data is normally distributed ($p < .001$), confirming that the composite data related to patient safety rating was not normally

distributed (i.e., non-parametric) (Curtin University, n.d.). Therefore, subsequent data analysis was performed using the Mann-Whitney U and the Kruskal Wallis nonparametric tests.

Differences in Type of Staff Position and Perceptions

A comparison of anesthesia provider types was performed to achieve the project aim of assessing demographic data and differences in responses for different composite scores. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists based on their responses along the highest composite measure (Teamwork) and the lowest composite measure (Staffing). The mean rank for CRNAs was lower than physician anesthesiologists for both Teamwork (*20.64 vs. 30.42*) and Staffing composite measures (*20.61 vs. 30.58*). However, the Mann-Whitney U test revealed that these differences between CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists were not statistically significant at the $p < .05$ level.

A comparison of the average patient safety rating between CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists was also performed. Similar to the composite measures discussed above, the mean rank for CRNAs was lower than physician anesthesiologists (*21.49 vs. 25.17*). However, the Mann-Whitney U test revealed that this difference was not statistically significant at the $p < .05$ level. The null hypothesis was retained, indicating there was no relationship between provider subtype and patient safety rating.

Differences in Tenure and Perceptions

The Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to explore the impact of years worked in the department on the highest (Teamwork) and lowest (Staffing) composite scores for all participants (i.e., CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists). There were no statistically significant differences at the $p < .05$ level in Teamwork and Staffing composite scores for the different levels of years worked in the department for all participants.

The Kruskal-Wallis test was performed to explore the impact of years worked in the department on all participants' average patient safety ratings. There was no statistically significant difference at the $p < .05$ level in average patient safety ratings for the different levels of years worked in department for all participants.

Correlation Between Composite Measures

Correlational tests were used to explore relationships between average scores and composite measures and between demographic data and composite measures using Spearman Rank Order Correlation (Rho). There were strong, positive correlations between the Teamwork composite measure and Organizational Learning ($r = .51, n = 43, p < .001$), Response to Error ($r = .62, n = 43, p < .001$), and Communication About Error ($r = .51, n = 43, p < .001$). Therefore, higher Teamwork scores were associated with higher Organizational Learning, Response to Error, and Communication About Error. Looking at the questions that make up each of those composite measures and relating them to the composite measure of Teamwork, links between responses to error from a teamwork mindset can be seen in relation to PSC. For example, within Response to Error there is a question stating, “When staff make errors, this unit focuses on learning rather than blaming individuals.” The question denotes a teamwork mentality, where respondents work towards a shared goal of PSC rather than being blamed for mistakes that have occurred. The average scoring for this question was 3.63, which indicates a generally positive perception from respondents. The strong correlation between the two composite measures related to error and the Teamwork composite can be utilized for future development of patient safety quality improvement measures.

Another composite measure with statistically significant positive correlations was Organizational Learning. The Spearman's rank order was performed between Organizational

Learning and other composite measures, and strong positive correlations were found between the Supervisor, Manager, or Clinical Leader Support for Patient Safety composite ($r = .70, n=43, p < .001$), and the Hospital Management Support for Patient Safety composite ($r = .63, n = 43, p < .001$).

The Communication About Error composite had strong positive correlations to the composite measures of Response to Error ($r = .54, n = 43, p < .001$) and Communication Openness ($r = .62, n = 43, p < .001$) after performing a Spearman rank order. The Communication Openness composite also had a strong positive correlation to the composite measure of Hospital Management Support for Safety ($r = .61, n = 43, p < .001$).

No statistically significant positive correlations existed after performing a Spearman rank order for the lowest averaged composite measure (Staffing) and the other composite measures. Likewise, staff position and years worked in the department yielded no significant correlation with the composite measures.

Comparison of Facility Results to National Database

The team utilized the AHRQ's SOPS Hospital Survey 2.0 Excel tool to input aggregate data and compare results to 400 other hospitals collected into the 2022 SOPS Hospital 2.0 database (AHRQ, 2022b). All composite measures had a lower percentage of positive responses compared to the national average. For example, the highest-scoring composite measure for the facility, Teamwork, had a 71% positive response compared to a national average of 80% (AHRQ, 2022b). The lowest-scoring composite measure of Staffing had a 20% positive response rate at the facility studied, compared with a national average of 51% (AHRQ, 2022b).

A comparison of the number of patient safety events reported by the facility against the national average revealed that 40% of respondents within our study reported no patient safety

events in the previous 12 months, in comparison to 55% of respondents in the AHRQ national database (AHRQ, 2022b). Fifty-one percent of respondents in our study, compared to 27% of respondents in the AHRQ database, reported one to two safety events in the previous 12 months, demonstrating a higher rate of reporting safety events within our study respondents than the national average. While the national average is lower than our survey's average, it is unclear if differences result from a higher percentage of safety events occurring within the facility or a culture in which respondents are more likely to report safety events without fear of penalization.

Thematic Analysis

In addition to the quantitative aspect of data analysis and the SOPS 2.0 survey, the survey included a free text section allowing respondents to write comments about their perception of PSC. Five respondents provided additional comments to their surveys, allowing the team to perform a thematic analysis of their comments, as shown in Figure 5.

Staffing Shortages

The first theme was associated with the drawbacks of ongoing staffing shortages. Four respondents reported that staffing shortages had placed an “inordinate burden on existing practitioners.” In addition, a lack of adequate anesthesia providers to perform patient care duties has had untoward effects on provider burnout. One respondent noted that an inadequate workforce, unusual working hours, and resulting provider burnout can “negatively impact patient safety and compromise the quality of care.” This theme suggests that providers have concerns regarding patient safety in the presence of acute and long-term staffing shortages. Furthermore, these statements are consistent with the findings of Azyabi et al. (2021), which demonstrate that work overload and the associated burden negatively influence the quality of care delivered and the perceptions of PSC by providers.

Supervisor, Manager, or Clinical Leaders Support for Patient Safety Concerns and Communication Openness

The second emerging theme details the administrative staff's need for more support and communication openness. One respondent described that their managers "do not understand the work performed by the clinicians," yet they "participate in too many ways that affect patients in a negative manner." This theme highlights the need for more effective clinical leadership and support for their staff. The survey findings add to the existing literature, demonstrating that leaders can effectively demonstrate support for patient safety by allotting time with staff to communicate safety concerns (Lotfi et al., 2018). This response emphasizes an area of improvement for leadership support when improving PSC. Moreover, the respondent stated, "when issues are brought to the managers, they choose to ignore them due to their fear and lack of knowledge." As Lotfi et al. (2018) state, effective managers must actively listen to their staff's safety challenges to effect positive change. This respondent's response suggests that increased communication openness between the managers of the anesthesia department and anesthesia providers is needed to improve the PSC within this facility.

Continuous Organizational Learning

The final theme identified was the importance of continuous and organizational learning. One respondent stated, "the department should also establish a collaboration between the quality improvement department and KPSA DNP students and graduates that can have the skills and tools necessary for improving patient care." This observation is congruent with the findings of Amiri et al. (2018), who found a positive correlation between active continuous processes within an organization and staff perception of PSC. This response suggests that the facility should

improve communication and strengthen partnerships with KPSA, which may lead to quality improvement projects that increase patient safety within the anesthesia department.

Discussion

The most critical step in establishing a safety culture is obtaining a baseline assessment of the current state of PSC. With the guidance of the revised Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice as a framework, the team was able to complete the project's aims of assessing the PSC within an anesthesia department and providing recommendations for improvement (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). To assess the current state of PSC within the department, the team utilized the validated AHRQ SOPS 2.0 survey (Reis et al., 2018).

A total response rate of 35.5% was attained, with an online survey response rate greater than 30% deemed acceptable by Wu et al. (2022). The average national response rates for online surveys range from 34-36 % (Wu et al., 2022). While all respondents were anesthesia providers, the majority (80%) were CRNAs, and none were department managers or leaders. Future and more comprehensive departmental assessment of PSC should employ strategies to include managerial insight and garner increased survey responses from physician anesthesiologists.

Strong areas of PSC were noted in the dimensions of Teamwork (71%) and Communication About Error (65%). Similar findings are seen in the 2022 AHRQ database, with the dimension of Teamwork having the highest positive response rate (82%). In addition, there was no statistically significant difference in overall patient safety rating or positive response rate in the dimension of Teamwork between providers of different tenures or between CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists. These findings contrast with a similar study by Makary et al. (2006), which found that within the operating room, anesthesiologists expressed greater satisfaction with collaboration between physicians and nurses than CRNAs. These differences were postulated to result from inherent differences in provider roles, input, and perceived authority (Makary et al., 2006). The similar perception of teamwork and PSC by physician anesthesiologists and CRNAs

may indicate an overall positive collegial relationship within the department. However, a more balanced sample of provider subtypes is needed to support this claim. Khalafi et al. (2023) found that collegial, interdisciplinary relationships and effective teamwork between CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists set a precedent for a productive and safe practicing environment. Thus, if teamwork is perceived as appropriate for a culture of safety, then interventions for improvement of PSC in this facility should be aimed toward areas with a greater need for improvement.

Approximately 49% of respondents had a positive overall patient safety rating of their department, denoting significant improvement opportunities. The lowest positive response rates were seen in Staffing (21%) and Hospital Management Support for Patient Safety (33%), making these dimensions suitable targets for PSC improvement. Similarly, the 2022 AHRQ database denoted Staffing as the dimension with the lowest positive response rate (51%), indicating that staffing shortages may be a widespread challenge. However, the team's results showed a 30% lower rating in Staffing than the benchmark rate seen in the AHRQ's database. These findings suggest that most anesthesia providers within the department feel staffing or workplace conditions need to be improved to support safe patient care and workflow processes. The qualitative findings of this survey also highlighted staffing inadequacies, increased workload, long working hours, and increased provider burnout as patient safety concerns.

Addressing understaffing is critical to ensure the delivery of quality care and meeting the production demands of the OR. High provider turnover can cause a redistribution of workload burdens on existing staff, leading to increased working hours, workplace stress, pressure for productivity, provider burnout, and provider exodus (Lea et al., 2022; Mahoney et al., 2020). Burnout, defined as an inability to cope with long-term workplace stress leading to psychological

exhaustion and disengagement, has several modifiable risk factors (Lea et al., 2022). These risk factors are poor leadership, excessive workloads, poor work/life balance, ineffective collegial communication, and decreased provider input in work environments (Dalton, 2021). A relationship exists between increased provider burnout and decreased job satisfaction, patient safety, and clinician productivity (Mahoney et al., 2020). Diminished provider productivity due to burnout may manifest as increased sick hours, leading to the underutilization of operating rooms and a breach in delivering safe and timely patient care (Dalton, 2021). Additionally, several factors may contribute to a higher perception of staffing inadequacies, including inadequate departmental planning and coordination, underutilization of supportive technology or staff, and increased patient complexity (Aljaffary et al., 2021). Targeting interventions to modify the mentioned risk factors for staffing shortages and provider burnout can improve PSC perception within the select anesthesia department.

The AHRQ database depicts Leader Support for Patient Safety as the composite measure with the second-highest positive response rate (AHRQ, 2022b). This finding contrasts with the results of this project, which indicated that most anesthesia providers within the department did not perceive leadership as supporting a culture of patient safety. The discrepancy may be attributed to organizational contextual factors such as a potential need for more emphasis on PSC education, training, and management support. In addition, while Communication About Error is the dimension with the second highest positive response rate, Leadership Support for Patient Safety had lower positive response rates. This disparity may be related to various factors, including a need for more frequent managerial feedback, safety culture training, or more effective safety policies. Moreover, although errors and system vulnerabilities are openly communicated and reported, it is possible that improvements to mitigate the identified risks are

not consistently implemented or prioritized by leaders. The qualitative findings further support these disparities and indicate a disconnect between frontline providers and leaders, as providers feel their voiced patient safety concerns and suggestions are not heard or addressed by leaders in the department. Lea et al. (2022) indicated poor leadership contributes to decreased job satisfaction, provider burnout, and an inability to retain staff. However, managers are often not included in PSC assessment (Lofti et al., 2018). Investigating leadership perceptions of PSC is equally crucial in identifying any potential divergence from the perceptions of frontline providers. A gap in PSC perceptions may suggest a need to institute leadership or staff PSC training programs to create a more coherent, united, and safe practicing environment (Montminy, 2022).

An effective leader systematically promotes and empowers providers to prioritize a safety climate while ensuring a speak-up and just culture built on mutual trust (Han et al., 2019). To do this, leaders must receive proper training on evidence-based processes and methods that help build an influential safety culture (Montminy, 2022; Ree & Wiig, 2019). Therefore, targeting interventions to transform the department's leadership values and styles may provide meaningful positive change in the organization's PSC.

Recommendations

Proactively addressing staffing shortages, provider burnout, and retention is imperative to avert negative impacts on patient safety and the quality of care delivered (Dalton, 2021; Mahoney et al., 2020). A recommendation and crucial first step toward increasing the retention of anesthesia providers is to monitor and assess for provider turnover and retention trends (Tang & Hudson, 2019). Assessing turnover patterns within specific demographic groups may cue leadership into potential causes of high turnover and subsequent solutions (Tang & Hudson,

2019). More importantly, administrators should assess turnover intention, or the intent to resign or seek alternative employment, before turnover occurs (Mahoney et al., 2020). Furthermore, assessing job satisfaction through staff interviews or surveys can provide relevant information regarding potential provider losses (Mahoney et al., 2020). Mahoney et al. (2020) found that regardless of demographic variables, the two most prevalent reasons CRNAs intended to leave their workplace were to seek more acceptable working environments and increased pay. Creating a workplace with healthy and supportive provider-manager relationships, shared governance, increased autonomy and skillset, competitive pay, and reasonable working hours can prevent the financial and PSC culture burden incurred by high turnover and staffing shortages (Lea et al., 2022; Mahoney et al., 2020; Tang & Hudson, 2019).

Several strategies are recommended to improve high turnover and staffing, including intensifying recruitment efforts, increasing provider autonomy by allowing shared governance, avoiding limiting the scope of practice, and allowing decision-making in matters that affect their practice (Lea et al., 2022; Mahoney et al., 2020; Tang & Hudson, 2019). Mahoney et al.'s (2020) findings suggest that job satisfaction and provider burnout were improved most by increasing provider autonomy. Thus, devising interventions to increase provider autonomy should be a departmental priority in mitigating provider loss. The formation of CRNA and physician anesthesiologist committees and councils can allow providers an avenue to voice concerns regarding operational challenges, collaborate, and promote staff engagement and involvement in addressing patient safety matters (Tang & Hudson, 2019). Developing a committee for provider recruitment and retention may be of particular interest.

Work-life balance has also shown increasing importance in determining job satisfaction (Lea et al., 2022; Tang & Hudson, 2019). Excessive overtime, call, or working hours were

among the top three reasons for provider burnout, along with insufficient pay and exorbitant workload pressures (Mahoney et al., 2020; Tang & Hudson, 2019). Leadership should support flexibility in generating work schedules to allow providers to schedule professional advancement opportunities, conferences, or address family matters (Tang & Hudson, 2019). Organizational strategies to ensure schedule flexibility include allowing part-time employment, ensuring work activities fall within working hours, and honoring personal responsibilities when scheduling work-related meetings (West et al., 2018). To minimize excessive workload, leaders should ensure the adequacy of supportive staff and assign clear roles to offload nonclinical work from clinicians (West et al., 2018).

Managerial support for patient safety is critical in forming a positive PSC within a healthcare organization or team (Mahoney et al., 2020). Among physician anesthesiologists and CRNAs, burnout and intent to resign decreased when providers perceived leadership as supportive (Lea et al., 2022). Several recommendations may be helpful to improve clinician perceptions of leadership's support for patient safety. First, leaders and frontline staff alike should be provided extensive and regular PSC education and training to build the knowledge and skills necessary to promote, develop, and improve safety climates and initiatives (Haskins & Roets, 2022). Efforts by leadership to create a work environment built on communication openness and a mutual understanding of the importance of patient safety are recommended to improve PSC (Tang & Hudson, 2019). Haskins and Roets (2022) suggest that leaders engage clinicians in quality improvement initiatives and do so supportively. Additionally, managers should demonstrate participative leadership by actively engaging with clinicians, assessing frontline workflows, communicating outcomes data, being available and visible to staff for concerns, and developing corrective actions for raised safety concerns (Haskins & Roets, 2022;

Mahoney et al., 2020; Tang & Hudson, 2019). A culture in which providers are encouraged to speak up regarding safety concerns without fear of retribution allows for the timely resolution of patient and employee safety threats (Haskins & Roets, 2022; Tang & Hudson, 2019).

Furthermore, providers who lead safety initiatives, identify potential threats to patient safety or formulate effective solutions should be recognized and rewarded for their efforts (Tang & Hudson, 2019). Acknowledgment and recognition can be provided by leadership, patients, or colleagues, both publicly and privately, to demonstrate appreciation for their hard work and efforts (Haskins & Roets, 2022; Tang & Hudson, 2019).

Wellness and mindfulness-based interventions may help decrease potential burnout in healthcare providers (Sultana et al., 2020). Additionally, preparing and making clinicians aware of the potential for burnout during forecasted staffing shortages can build mental fortitude and resilience preemptively, a characteristic linked to decreased burnout (Sultana et al., 2020). Bringing awareness can allow providers to feel supported, as leadership acknowledges the mental health burden caused by increased workplace stress and demands (Mahoney et al., 2020; Sultana et al., 2020). Providing workshops on burnout, coping, and resilience-building can facilitate stress reduction within the workplace (Sultana et al., 2020). More importantly, including providers in decision-making regarding what wellness-based activities may build resilience and improve provider stress imparts a sense of control over their workplace environment (Tang & Hudson; Sultana et al., 2020). Interventions to improve stress management, wellness, and open communication of updates will provide clinicians with the necessary tools to maintain engagement and patient safety standards (Sultana et al., 2020).

Sustainability

Despite these recommendations, the literature suggests that creating sustainable, permanent change may prove challenging for clinicians and facilities (Cullen et al., 2022). It is crucial to identify implementation strategies tailored to this specific facility at KP SBC. The Iowa Implementation for Sustainability Framework (IISF) is an application model that includes 81 distinctive implementation strategies with timing suggestions to guide the implementation of evidence-based healthcare strategies (Cullen et al., 2022). The IISF provides discrete, actionable strategies that can be used by both novices and experts, thus providing a guide for nurses, interprofessional teams, and other healthcare providers to implement and sustain evidence-based recommendations efficiently (Cullen et al., 2022). The facility can follow the IISF to adopt sustainable recommendations that endure future challenges after identifying discrete strategies and operationalizing measurable goals to improve PSC.

According to the IISF, the first step to creating sustainable change is identifying and engaging key personnel (Cullen et al., 2022). The recommendations to improve staffing at KP SBC may be accomplished with anesthesia department leaders posting frequent job postings to recruit additional anesthesia providers to work at KP SBC. The job postings will be on the KP website, and word-of-mouth recruitment will also be spread to garner interest in working at KP SBC. As KP SBC has a partnership with KPSA, additional efforts will be made by anesthesia department leadership to recruit new graduate nurse anesthetists to consider KP SBC for employment after graduation. Bi-annual recruitment emails will be mailed to clinical faculty at KPSA, who will then disseminate the hiring information to current KPSA DNP students in their final year of school. Additionally, anesthesia department leaders and clinical liaisons from KP

SBC may hold regular, virtual, and in-person hiring fairs to generate interest and answer questions from prospective applicants.

Developing a committee will require buy-in from current anesthesia department leaders, CRNAs, and physician anesthesiologists. As the key stakeholders will be anesthesia providers, they must be actively involved in shared governance committees to brainstorm strategies to improve provider recruitment and retention. Perhaps more importantly, managers and supervisors must also have a voice on the committees, as increased supervisor support is one of the key variables that increases staff perception of PSC (Abuosi et al., 2022).

After identifying and engaging key personnel, it is time to hardwire the change into the system. This change can be accomplished at KP SBC by establishing monthly meetings for the retention and recruitment committees. Having recurring, scheduled meetings may help create lasting, sustainable change as operational challenges and staffing concerns will be brought up monthly. Meetings ensure that clinical anesthesia staff have a set time to voice their concerns about PSC while providing scheduled intervals to check the climate regarding current PSC challenges. Another method of hardwiring the change of wellness and mindfulness interventions into the culture at KP SBC is to hold monthly department wellness sessions where staff can relax with aromatherapy, massage chairs, and meditative music. Creating an open space where anesthesia staff can unwind in the middle of their day may decrease burnout in the anesthesia department, ultimately creating higher staff perceptions of PSC (Zamanifar et al., 2020).

Once the recommendations have been implemented, the next step is to monitor key indicators through quality improvement (Cullen et al., 2022). The key indicators can be measured at monthly shared governance meetings through questionnaires that utilize a 5-point Likert scale to assess staff perceptions of PSC. The scores will be tallied monthly, and the results

will be shared at the next committee meeting. An area for free text comments will also be available for staff members to provide recommendations or voice PSC concerns. Based on the results of the monthly surveys, the recruitment and retention committee leaders may work alongside the clinical managers and anesthesia department administrative staff to tailor future recommendations, which is the last step of the Iowa Model Implementation for Sustainability Framework (Cullen et al., 2022). By identifying and engaging key personnel through active recruitment of additional anesthesia personnel, establishing a shared governance committee focusing on staff recruitment and retention, and monitoring key indicators through monthly questionnaires and check-ins at regular intervals, KP SBC can create enduring change to increase PSC that will be engrained in the culture of their anesthesia department.

Implications

Evidence demonstrates the implications of a positive PSC and the correlation with the frequency of AE reporting. Abuosi et al. (2022) show that increased scores in dimensions of PSC show a strong positive correlation between the frequency of AE reporting. Additionally, there are noted increases in staff perception of teamwork, organizational learning, response to error, and supervisor support for patient safety (Abuosi et al., 2022). Adverse event reporting can take the form of many examples, including identifying medication errors, recounting near misses, as well as documenting system errors that require deeper root cause analysis to prevent future errors from occurring. Anesthesia medication errors and AEs must first be acknowledged for the pharmacy department to take the initiative in preventing their continued occurrence. For example, administering high-alert medications such as insulin or heparin would usually require a double check by two nurses before being given to a patient; however, anesthesia providers may not be required to scan medications before administering them. Critical alert messages on the

electronic administration record may prevent inadvertent administration of the incorrect medication or dose, thus preventing an AE.

Additionally, Abuosi et al. (2022) found that communication about errors in healthcare settings was increased when staff felt a greater perception of teamwork with their coworkers. The highest-scoring variables included communication about errors, response to errors, handoffs, and information exchange (Abuosi et al., 2022). When staff feel it is safe to report AEs, they may be more inclined to report their and their colleagues' errors. However, when staff report increased negative PSC scores with lower predictive variables in teamwork and supervisor support for patient safety, they may feel that reporting AEs may lead to detrimental events, such as punitive responses from their supervisors (Abuosi et al., 2022). Unfortunately, this may lead to decreased patient safety, diminished quality of care, and potentially negative patient outcomes.

Positive PSC scores are instrumental and seen in the literature as a significant indicator for AE reporting (Abuosi et al., 2022). Medication errors within hospital facilities will occur; however, it is up to the staff to feel that it is a safe environment and healthy PSC to report their errors. When a facility displays higher PSC scores, particularly in the variables of teamwork and communication, the quality of healthcare and patient safety can be improved, and the delivery of quality patient care is enhanced.

Strengths, Barriers, and Limitations

Strengths

One of the strengths of this project was the survey response rate of 35.5%, which allowed for an adequate sample size of participants to perform data analysis. The response rate allowed the team to accomplish the study's aims, including assessing the PSC of the facility and assessing the highest and lowest composite measures and if there were any differences between

demographic subgroups. By determining the areas of strength and weakness, the group was able to provide recommendations that will allow future patient safety quality improvement projects at the facility a foundation for implementation. Further studies at the facility can focus on safety issues related to specific composite measures, for example, the composite measure of Staffing and its impact on adverse patient safety events such as medication errors.

A validated tool such as the AHRQ SOPS 2.0 also strengthened the project. Using a validated tool allows for an accurate depiction of a PSC for a facility and the reliability of results representing the dimensions of the PSC. The use of the AHRQ SOPS 2.0 Hospital survey is beneficial because it allows not just a current rendering of PSC for a facility but the ability to assess PSC after future change measures for quality improvement or to provide a longitudinal depiction of the facility's evolving PSC (Sorra & Dyer, 2010). Additionally, using a tool like the AHRQ SOPS 2.0 strengthens the project because it has been used nationally and globally, and results from this study can be compared to national benchmarks to assess the facility's perceptions of PSC rank compared to national averages. Because the tool is also linked to a national database, a strength of this project is that it adds to the growing body of evidence for assessing PSC within a hospital and how reviewing a PSC can lead to better patient safety outcomes.

Another strength was using an online or electronic survey, which increased the ease of data extraction, preserved anonymity, and allowed for implementation to be cost-effective (Sammut et al., 2021; Shiyab et al., 2023). The group collected data in real time and began looking at trends in the data during the survey period. The use of an online survey also allowed the group to prevent duplicate or illegitimate entries via the use of an authenticator.

Barriers and Limitations

The most prominent barrier during the implementation stage was the engagement of survey participants. While a participation rate of 35.5% was achieved, the group had to reframe the approach to participant engagement throughout the survey period to reach that number. The group initially leaned on email campaigns for survey participation, but analytics from Qualtrics demonstrated a low engagement rate with each email reminder. The group then pivoted to the heavy use of a survey champion who could motivate individuals to take the survey and was present in the facility to engage participants on any questions regarding the survey and to provide guidance on how to access the survey. Another barrier to the implementation of the survey was survey link errors. One of the email reminders had a truncated survey link and, therefore, did not bring participants to the survey. The email, distributed on June 20, 2023, featured a hyperlink that did not direct users to the survey, and because of this, some participants may have been lost.

Despite the survey response rate of 35.5%, limitations exist with the data set obtained. The 43 responses, while able to provide an accurate representation of the PSC of the facility, may not be generalizable to other facilities or anesthesia departments. Of the 43 participants, only six were physician anesthesiologists, which may equate to an underrepresentation of this demographic subgroup within the data and the overall perceptions of PSC. Additionally, the group utilized convenience sampling, opening the survey collection to all individuals who were direct anesthesia care providers. While this allowed all providers to respond and voice their perception of PSC, it may have led to a sampling of providers with certain biases (positive or negative) and a skewing of the sample data.

Similarly, the lack of response from other providers can create bias, wherein the perceptions of those who do not complete the survey are lost and are underrepresented in the

sample data (Ellis et al., 2022). Some reasons for a lack of survey engagement regarding safety culture can come from a lack of buy-in from participants, a lack of available time to complete the survey, and survey fatigue (Ellis et al., 2022). Future efforts for surveys and assessing staff perceptions of PSC at this facility should focus on staff engagement, with strategies building on the ones employed for this project. Predictors of higher response rate in surveys for patient safety include face-to-face engagement by the team administering the survey, consideration of also using a non-electronic survey method, which may allow hospital staff workers to complete the survey on their own time without fear of taking away from patient care, and timing survey distribution to ensure that staff is not currently engaged in other surveys or quality improvement projects (Ellis et al., 2022).

Conclusion

The assessment of organizational PSC has become an essential component of risk reduction within healthcare systems. As a measurement tool, surveys assessing PSC provide a valuable glimpse into how an organization's current processes, norms, and values influence perceived patient safety from within (Reis et al., 2018). Various cultural attributes have been studied and regarded as contributing to enhanced safety culture, including leadership support for patient safety, a nonpunitive response to errors, teamwork, provider engagement, communication, staffing, and organizational learning (Arzahan et al., 2022; Reis et al., 2018). Current literature supports using the AHRQ's SOPS 2.0 survey to assess PSC due to its measurement of the relevant attributes mentioned earlier (Waterson et al., 2019). With proper dissemination and implementation, survey results can facilitate targeted improvement efforts to strengthen patient safety (Waterson et al., 2019). Consequently, safety culture assessment has become increasingly appealing within poorly studied disciplines, such as the field of anesthesia (Arzahan et al., 2022).

This project aimed to gain a baseline assessment of the PSC within the anesthesia department at two sister hospitals in Southern California and subsequently provide recommendations to strengthen weaknesses in PSC identified through survey results. The results indicated that the PSC dimensions of Teamwork and Communication about error had the highest positive response rate. Conversely, the dimensions of Staffing and Manager Support for Patient Safety had the lowest positive response rates, demonstrating congruence with the AHRQ results database and indicating that these components were potential areas for improvement within the project implementation site. A qualitative analysis of free-text comments was undertaken and reinforced that staffing, provider burnout, and a lack of managerial support for patient safety

were priorities for improvement. Recommendations were provided to improve provider burnout, clinician retention, stress management, and the provider-leader relationship.

Implementing the recommended interventions is highly complex and context-specific. Further studies investigating effective interventions for improving staffing and provider burnout are necessary to provide superior resolution. Although the cause implicated in staffing shortages remains unclear, assessing for turnover trends, provider job satisfaction, burnout, and turnover intent through surveys, one-on-one interviews, group discussions, or suggestion boxes may lend further insight into potential facility-dependent causes. However, as leadership support for patient safety has been shown to increase PSC and job satisfaction, targeted improvements in this area can effectuate positive changes in staffing patterns and PSC. Further, re-evaluating PSC perceptions is equally important in determining whether integrated interventions were effective.

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APPENDIX A

Figure 1: The Revised Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Figure 1

The Revised Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Note. Revised Iowa Model of Evidence-Based practice used as a supporting framework for the research project to guide project direction. (Image used with written permission from the University of Iowa.)

APPENDIX B

Figure 2: Timeline of Project Tasks and Completion Dates

Figure 2

Timeline of Project Tasks and Completion Dates

Task	Proposed Date
Proposal defense	December 2022
Application for Kaiser IRB approval	January 2023
Application for CSUF IRB approval	February 2023
Upload AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 onto Qualtrics	March 2023
Discussion of the survey with the facility's anesthesia department (pending IRB approval)	Spring 2023
Distribution of survey to sample population	May 2023 to July 2023
End of the survey and data analysis begins	July 2023
Data analysis	July 2023 to October 2023
Completion of the project and final write-up	December 2023
Dissemination of findings	January 2024

APPENDIX C

Figure 3: Evaluation and Measurement of Outcomes

Figure 3

Evaluation and Measurement of Outcomes

Outcome	Operational Definition	Method of Measurement	Analysis
Assess attitudes related to PSC	Surveys on attitudes related to PSC	AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 tool	Averages of aggregate data for each dimension of Hospital SOPS 2.0
	Thematic analysis of comments related to patient safety		Identification and coding of comments until thematic saturation is reached
Provide recommendations for PSC gaps and opportunities for improvement	Measurement of highest and lowest composite scores of PSC	AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 results	Qualitative analysis

Assess demographic data and differences in responses for each composite score	Comparison of average scores for each dimension against each demographic category	AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 results	Descriptive analysis of demographic data Statistical, comparative, and correlational analysis
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APPENDIX D

Figure 4: Histogram Depicting Distribution of Patient Safety Rating Scores

APPENDIX E

Figure 5: Description of Emerging Themes

Figure 5

Description of Emerging Themes

Staffing shortages

<i>Subcategories</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Significant Statement Examples</i>
Shift types	Specific shifts create higher burdens on anesthesia providers	"These are often undesirable shifts: 24 hours, weekends, nights, or on-call. Burnout will negatively impact patient safety and compromise the quality of care"
Limited resources	Lack of resources may compromise quality of patient care	<p>"However, when there is limited time, resources, and people it is very challenging to implement quality improvement processes and to do the necessary follow-up to determine if a true change has occurred"</p> <p>"Staffing shortages need long term solutions"</p> <p>"Increase in staff will always help decrease stress on current staff from becoming overworked and burned out"</p> <p>"Adequate staffing and resources for staff to perform thier [sic] job duties"</p>

Time constraints	Time limitations may hinder quality improvement initiatives	"However, when there is limited time, resources, and people it is very challenging to implement quality improvement processes and to do the necessary follow-up to determine if a true change has occurred"
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**Supervisor,
Manager, or
Clinical
Leaders
Support for
Patient Safety
Concerns/Com
munication
Openness**

Knowledgeable leadership	Leadership who possess strong clinical knowledge may promote positive change	""Our department has hired 3 RN managers for the anesthesia dept. They are good people in the wrong positions. They do not understand the work performed by the clinicians, yet they participate in too many ways that affect patients in a negative manner"
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Listening to staff concerns	Leadership who listen to staff may increase perception of patient safety	"When issues are brought to the managers, they choose to ignore them due to their fear and lack of knowledge"
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**Organizational
Learning/Continuous
Improvement**

Interdepartment collaboration	Collaboration between new anesthesia departments and new students may improve delivery of care	""... The department should also establish a collaboration between the quality improvement department and KPSA DNP students/graduates that can have the skills and tools necessary for improving patient care"
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Quality
improvement

Quality improvement
projects promote
positive change

“... The department should also establish
a collaboration between the quality improvement
department and KPSA DNP
students/graduates that can have the skills and tools
necessary for improving
patient care”

APPENDIX F

Image 1: Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture 2.0

Image 1

Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality's Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture 2.0

Hospital Survey on Patient Safety

Instructions

This survey asks for your opinions about patient safety issues, medical error, and event reporting in your hospital and will take about 10 to 15 minutes to complete.

If you do not wish to answer a question, or if a question does not apply to you, you may leave your answer blank.

- An **"event"** is defined as any type of error, mistake, incident, accident, or deviation, regardless of whether or not it results in patient harm.
- **"Patient safety"** is defined as the avoidance and prevention of patient injuries or adverse events resulting from the processes of health care delivery.

SECTION A: Your Work Area/Unit

In this survey, think of your "unit" as the work area, department, or clinical area of the hospital where you spend **most of your work time or provide most of your clinical services**.

What is your primary work area or unit in this hospital? Select ONE answer.

- a. Many different hospital units/No specific unit
- b. Medicine (non-surgical) h. Psychiatry/mental health n. Other, please specify:
- c. Surgery i. Rehabilitation
- d. Obstetrics j. Pharmacy
- e. Pediatrics k. Laboratory
- f. Emergency department l. Radiology
- g. Intensive care unit (any type) m. Anesthesiology

Please indicate your agreement or disagreement with the following statements about your work area/unit.

Think about your hospital work area/unit...	Strongly Disagree ▼	Disagree ▼	Neither ▼	Agree ▼	Strongly Agree ▼
1. People support one another in this unit	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
2. We have enough staff to handle the workload.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
3. When a lot of work needs to be done quickly, we work together as a team to get the work done	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
4. In this unit, people treat each other with respect	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
5. Staff in this unit work longer hours than is best for patient care.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

SECTION A: Your Work Area/Unit (continued)

	Strongly Disagree ▼	Disagree ▼	Neither ▼	Agree ▼	Strongly Agree ▼
Think about your hospital work area/unit...					
6. We are actively doing things to improve patient safety	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
7. We use more agency/temporary staff than is best for patient care	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
8. Staff feel like their mistakes are held against them	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
9. Mistakes have led to positive changes here	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
10. It is just by chance that more serious mistakes don't happen around here	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
11. When one area in this unit gets really busy, others help out	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
12. When an event is reported, it feels like the person is being written up, not the problem	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
13. After we make changes to improve patient safety, we evaluate their effectiveness	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
14. We work in "crisis mode" trying to do too much, too quickly	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
15. Patient safety is never sacrificed to get more work done	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
16. Staff worry that mistakes they make are kept in their personnel file	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
17. We have patient safety problems in this unit	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
18. Our procedures and systems are good at preventing errors from happening	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

SECTION B: Your Supervisor/Manager

Please indicate your agreement or disagreement with the following statements about your immediate supervisor/manager or person to whom you directly report.

	Strongly Disagree ▼	Disagree ▼	Neither ▼	Agree ▼	Strongly Agree ▼
1. My supervisor/manager says a good word when he/she sees a job done according to established patient safety procedures	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
2. My supervisor/manager seriously considers staff suggestions for improving patient safety	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
3. Whenever pressure builds up, my supervisor/manager wants us to work faster, even if it means taking shortcuts	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
4. My supervisor/manager overlooks patient safety problems that happen over and over	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

SECTION C: Communications

How often do the following things happen in your work area/unit?

	Never ▼	Rarely ▼	Some- times ▼	Most of the time ▼	Always ▼
Think about your hospital work area/unit...					
1. We are given feedback about changes put into place based on event reports.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
2. Staff will freely speak up if they see something that may negatively affect patient care	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
3. We are informed about errors that happen in this unit	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
4. Staff feel free to question the decisions or actions of those with more authority	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
5. In this unit, we discuss ways to prevent errors from happening again	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
6. Staff are afraid to ask questions when something does not seem right....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

SECTION D: Frequency of Events Reported

In your hospital work area/unit, when the following mistakes happen, how often are they reported?

	Never ▼	Rarely ▼	Some- times ▼	Most of the time ▼	Always ▼
1. When a mistake is made, but is <i>caught and corrected before affecting the patient</i> , how often is this reported?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
2. When a mistake is made, but has <i>no potential to harm the patient</i> , how often is this reported?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
3. When a mistake is made that <i>could harm the patient</i> , but does not, how often is this reported?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

SECTION E: Patient Safety Grade

Please give your work area/unit in this hospital an overall grade on patient safety.

<input type="checkbox"/>				
A	B	C	D	E
Excellent	Very Good	Acceptable	Poor	Failing

SECTION F: Your Hospital

Please indicate your agreement or disagreement with the following statements about your hospital.

	Strongly Disagree ▼	Disagree ▼	Neither ▼	Agree ▼	Strongly Agree ▼
Think about your hospital...					
1. Hospital management provides a work climate that promotes patient safety.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
2. Hospital units do not coordinate well with each other.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
3. Things "fall between the cracks" when transferring patients from one unit to another.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
4. There is good cooperation among hospital units that need to work together.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

SECTION F: Your Hospital (continued)

Think about your hospital...	Strongly Disagree ▼	Disagree ▼	Neither ▼	Agree ▼	Strongly Agree ▼
5. Important patient care information is often lost during shift changes	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
6. It is often unpleasant to work with staff from other hospital units	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
7. Problems often occur in the exchange of information across hospital units.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
8. The actions of hospital management show that patient safety is a top priority	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
9. Hospital management seems interested in patient safety only after an adverse event happens.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
10. Hospital units work well together to provide the best care for patients	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
11. Shift changes are problematic for patients in this hospital.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

SECTION G: Number of Events Reported

In the past 12 months, how many event reports have you filled out and submitted?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> a. No event reports | <input type="checkbox"/> d. 6 to 10 event reports |
| <input type="checkbox"/> b. 1 to 2 event reports | <input type="checkbox"/> e. 11 to 20 event reports |
| <input type="checkbox"/> c. 3 to 5 event reports | <input type="checkbox"/> f. 21 event reports or more |

SECTION H: Background Information

This information will help in the analysis of the survey results.

1. How long have you worked in this hospital?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> a. Less than 1 year | <input type="checkbox"/> d. 11 to 15 years |
| <input type="checkbox"/> b. 1 to 5 years | <input type="checkbox"/> e. 16 to 20 years |
| <input type="checkbox"/> c. 6 to 10 years | <input type="checkbox"/> f. 21 years or more |

2. How long have you worked in your current hospital work area/unit?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> a. Less than 1 year | <input type="checkbox"/> d. 11 to 15 years |
| <input type="checkbox"/> b. 1 to 5 years | <input type="checkbox"/> e. 16 to 20 years |
| <input type="checkbox"/> c. 6 to 10 years | <input type="checkbox"/> f. 21 years or more |

3. Typically, how many hours per week do you work in this hospital?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> a. Less than 20 hours per week | <input type="checkbox"/> d. 60 to 79 hours per week |
| <input type="checkbox"/> b. 20 to 39 hours per week | <input type="checkbox"/> e. 80 to 99 hours per week |
| <input type="checkbox"/> c. 40 to 59 hours per week | <input type="checkbox"/> f. 100 hours per week or more |

SECTION H: Background Information (continued)

4. What is your staff position in this hospital? Select ONE answer that best describes your staff position.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> a. Registered Nurse | <input type="checkbox"/> j. Respiratory Therapist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> b. Physician Assistant/Nurse Practitioner | <input type="checkbox"/> k. Physical, Occupational, or Speech Therapist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> c. LVN/LPN | <input type="checkbox"/> l. Technician (e.g., EKG, Lab, Radiology) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> d. Patient Care Asst/Hospital Aide/Care Partner | <input type="checkbox"/> m. Administration/Management |
| <input type="checkbox"/> e. Attending/Staff Physician | <input type="checkbox"/> n. Other, please specify: |
| <input type="checkbox"/> f. Resident Physician/Physician in Training | <input type="text"/> |
| <input type="checkbox"/> g. Pharmacist | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> h. Dietician | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> i. Unit Assistant/Clerk/Secretary | |

5. In your staff position, do you typically have direct interaction or contact with patients?

- a. YES, I typically have direct interaction or contact with patients.
- b. NO, I typically do NOT have direct interaction or contact with patients.

6. How long have you worked in your current specialty or profession?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> a. Less than 1 year | <input type="checkbox"/> d. 11 to 15 years |
| <input type="checkbox"/> b. 1 to 5 years | <input type="checkbox"/> e. 16 to 20 years |
| <input type="checkbox"/> c. 6 to 10 years | <input type="checkbox"/> f. 21 years or more |

SECTION I: Your Comments

Please feel free to write any comments about patient safety, error, or event reporting in your hospital.

THANK YOU FOR COMPLETING THIS SURVEY.

APPENDIX G

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Survey Respondents

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Survey Respondents

	<i>n</i>	%
Provider Classification		
APRNs	37	86%
Physician Anesthesiologists	6	14%
Tenure with Current Hospital		
Less than 1 year	2	5%
1 to 5 years	7	16%
6 to 10 years	18	42%
11 or more years	16	37%
Tenure in Current Unit/Work Area		
Less than 1 year	2	5%
1 to 5 years	8	19%
6 to 10 years	17	40%
11 or more years	16	37%
Hours Worked Per Week		
Less than 30 hours per week	8	19%
30 to 40 hours per week	12	28%
More than 40 hours per week	23	53%

APPENDIX H

Tables of Average Scores of Composite Questions

Table H1

Average Scores of Teamwork Composite Questions

Question	Average Score
In this unit, we work together as an effective team	3.86
During busy times, staff in this unit help each other	4.11
There is a problem with disrespectful behavior by those working in this unit	3.11*

Note: Items with asterisk were reverse coded to obtain composite average

Table H2

Average Scores of Staffing and Workplace Composite Questions

Question	Average Score
In this unit, we have enough staff to handle the workload	1.74
Staff in this unit work longer hours than is best for patient care	2.40*
This unit relies too much on temporary, float, or PRN staff	2.90*
The work pace in this unit is so rushed that it negatively affects patient safety	2.88*

Note: Items with asterisk were reverse coded to obtain composite average

Table H3*Average Scores of Organizational Learning Composite Questions*

Question	Average Score
This unit regularly reviews work processes to determine if changes are needed to improve patient safety	2.93
In this unit, changes to improve patient safety are evaluated to see how well they worked	3.30
This unit lets the same patient safety problems keep happening	3.13*

Note: Items with asterisk were reverse coded to obtain composite average

Table H4*Average Scores of Response to Error Composite Questions*

Question	Average Score
In this unit, staff feel like their mistakes are held against them	3.02*
When an event is reported in this unit, it feels like the person is being written up, not the problem	2.98*
When staff make errors, this unit focuses on learning rather than blaming individuals	3.63
In this unit, there is a lack of support for staff involved in patient safety errors	3.13*

Note: Items with asterisk were reverse coded to obtain composite average

Table H5*Average Scores of Supervisor, Manager, or Clinical Leader Support for Patient Safety**Composite Measure*

Question	Average Score
My supervisor, manager, or clinical leader seriously considers staff suggestions for improving patient safety	3.19
My supervisor, manager, or clinical leader wants us to work faster during busy times, even if it means taking shortcuts	3.26*
My supervisor, manager, or clinical leader takes action to address patient safety concerns that are brought to their attention	3.28

Note: Items with asterisk were reverse coded to obtain composite average

Table H6*Average Scores of Communication About Error Composite Measure*

Question	Average Score
We are informed about errors that happen in this unit	3.72
When errors happen in this unit, we discuss ways to prevent them from happening again	3.83
In this unit, we are informed about changes that are made based on event reports	3.60

Table H7*Average Scores of Communication Openness Composite Measure*

Question	Average Score
In this unit, staff speak up if they see something that may negatively affect patient care	3.88
When staff in this unit see someone with more authority doing something unsafe for patients, they speak up	3.74
When staff in this unit speak up, those with more authority are open to their patient safety concerns	3.47
In this unit, staff are afraid to ask questions when something does not seem right	3.56*

Note: Items with asterisk were reverse coded to obtain composite average

Table H8*Average Scores of Reporting Patient Safety Events Composite Measure*

Question	Average Score
When a mistake is caught and corrected before reaching the patient, how often is this reported?	3.37
When a mistake reaches the patient and could have harmed the patient, but did not, how often is this reported?	3.55

Note: Items with asterisk were reverse coded to obtain composite average

Table H9*Average Scores of Hospital Management Support For Patient Safety Composite*

Question	Average Score
The actions of hospital management show that patient safety is a top priority	3.07
Hospital management provides adequate resources to improve patient safety	2.88
Hospital management seems interested in patient safety only after an adverse event happens	2.06*

Note: Items with asterisk were reverse coded to obtain composite average

Table H10*Average Scores for Handoffs and Information Exchange Composite Measure*

Question	Average Score
When transferring patients from one unit to another, important information is often left out	3*
During shift changes, important patient care information is often left out	3.21*
During shift changes, there is adequate time to exchange all key patient care information	3.56

Note: Items with asterisk were reverse coded to obtain composite average